

Differential-Geometric Analysis of the Conical Helix

A Complete Treatment of Curvature, Torsion,
Frenet Frame, Arc Length, and Geometric Properties

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Abstract

This paper presents a complete differential-geometric analysis of the conical helix defined by the parametrization

$$\gamma(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{6}{\pi^2}\theta \cos(\theta) \\ \frac{6}{\pi^2}\theta \sin(\theta) \\ -\frac{3}{4} + \frac{3}{\pi}\theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad \theta \geq 0.$$

The curve combines the properties of an Archimedean spiral (in the xy -projection) with a linear increase in height, and lies entirely on the cone $z = -\frac{3}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2}r$. We compute in closed form: the tangent vector, principal normal, binormal (Frenet frame), curvature, torsion, arc length, pitch angle, and the asymptotic behaviour of all these quantities. A key result is that the spiral constant $a = 6/\pi^2 = 1/\zeta(2)$ connects number theory and differential geometry directly.

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1 Introduction and Background

1.1 The Conical Helix

A *helix* is a space curve that winds spirally around an axis [4, 5]. In the classical case of the *cylindrical helix*, the radius remains constant and both curvature and torsion are constant. The curve studied here is a fundamental generalisation: the radius grows linearly with the angle (Archimedean spiral), while the height also increases linearly. The curve therefore winds on a *cone* and is called a **conical helix**.

Definition 1.1 (Conical Helix). The conical helix is the space curve $\gamma : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ defined by:

$$\gamma(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{6}{\pi^2} \theta \cos(\theta) \\ \frac{6}{\pi^2} \theta \sin(\theta) \\ -\frac{3}{4} + \frac{3}{\pi} \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

with structural constants

$$a := \frac{6}{\pi^2} \approx 0.607927101854027, \quad b := \frac{3}{\pi} \approx 0.954929658551372. \quad (2)$$

Remark 1.1 (Structural Constants and the Basel Problem). The spiral constant $a = 6/\pi^2$ is the reciprocal of the famous Euler sum $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$, known as the Basel problem (L. Euler, 1734/1740) [16, 17]. The ratio of the two constants is remarkable:

$$\frac{b}{a} = \frac{3/\pi}{6/\pi^2} = \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (3)$$

As shown in Section 2, this ratio equals exactly the slope of the cone.

1.2 Component Form

In component form, Eq. (1) reads:

$$x(\theta) = a\theta \cos(\theta), \quad (4)$$

$$y(\theta) = a\theta \sin(\theta), \quad (5)$$

$$z(\theta) = -\frac{3}{4} + b\theta. \quad (6)$$

The xy -projection of γ is the *Archimedean spiral* $r(\theta) = a\theta$ [15, 14, 1], while $z(\theta)$ depends linearly on θ .

1.3 Regularity

Proposition 1.2 (Regularity). *The curve γ is regular for all $\theta > 0$, i.e. $\dot{\gamma}(\theta) \neq \mathbf{0}$.*

Proof. We have $\dot{z}(\theta) = b = 3/\pi > 0$ for all θ . Therefore the third component of the tangent vector is always non-zero, which implies $\dot{\gamma} \neq \mathbf{0}$. \square

2 Position on the Cone

Theorem 2.1 (Cone Equation). *The conical helix γ lies entirely on the cone*

$$\mathcal{K} := \left\{ (x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid z = -\frac{3}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \right\}. \quad (7)$$

Proof. The distance of a curve point from the z -axis is:

$$r(\theta) = \sqrt{x(\theta)^2 + y(\theta)^2} = \sqrt{a^2\theta^2 \cos^2 \theta + a^2\theta^2 \sin^2 \theta} = a\theta.$$

Substituting into the right-hand side of Eq. (7):

$$-\frac{3}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2} \cdot a\theta = -\frac{3}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{6}{\pi^2} \theta = -\frac{3}{4} + \frac{3}{\pi} \theta = z(\theta).$$

□

Corollary 2.2 (Cone Slope). *The slope of the cone generator is $\pi/2$; the corresponding cone angle from the horizontal (xy -plane) is:*

$$\psi_{\mathcal{K}} = \arctan\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \approx 57.518^\circ. \quad (8)$$

Remark 2.1 (Two Cone Angles). Two different angles are used in the literature to characterise a cone, depending on convention:

- The *elevation angle from the horizontal* (from the xy -plane): $\psi_{\mathcal{K}} = \arctan(\pi/2) \approx 57.52^\circ$.
- The *opening half-angle from the rotation axis* (from the z -axis): $\alpha = \arctan(2/\pi) \approx 32.48^\circ$.

Both angles are complementary: $\psi_{\mathcal{K}} + \alpha = 90^\circ$.

3 Tangent Vector and Arc Length

3.1 Tangent Vector

Proposition 3.1 (Tangent Vector). *The tangent vector $\dot{\gamma}(\theta)$ is:*

$$\dot{\gamma}(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} a(\cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta) \\ a(\sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta) \\ b \end{pmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Proposition 3.2 (Speed).

$$|\dot{\gamma}(\theta)| = \sqrt{a^2(1 + \theta^2) + b^2}. \quad (10)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
|\dot{\gamma}|^2 &= a^2(\cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta)^2 + a^2(\sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta)^2 + b^2 \\
&= a^2 [\cos^2 \theta - 2\theta \sin \theta \cos \theta + \theta^2 \sin^2 \theta] \\
&\quad + a^2 [\sin^2 \theta + 2\theta \sin \theta \cos \theta + \theta^2 \cos^2 \theta] + b^2 \\
&= a^2 \left[\underbrace{\cos^2 \theta + \sin^2 \theta}_{=1} + \theta^2 \underbrace{(\sin^2 \theta + \cos^2 \theta)}_{=1} \right] + b^2 \\
&= a^2(1 + \theta^2) + b^2.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 3.3 (Initial Speed). *Bei $\theta = 0$ gilt:*

$$|\dot{\gamma}(0)| = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} = \sqrt{\frac{36}{\pi^4} + \frac{9}{\pi^2}} = \frac{3}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{4}{\pi^2} + 1} \approx 1.13202.$$

Corollary 3.4 (Asymptotic Speed). *For $\theta \rightarrow \infty$:*

$$|\dot{\gamma}(\theta)| \sim a\theta = \frac{6}{\pi^2}\theta.$$

3.2 Second and Third Derivatives

Proposition 3.5 (Second Derivative).

$$\ddot{\gamma}(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} a(-2 \sin \theta - \theta \cos \theta) \\ a(2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

Proposition 3.6 (Third Derivative).

$$\ddot{\gamma}(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} a(-3 \cos \theta + \theta \sin \theta) \\ a(-3 \sin \theta - \theta \cos \theta) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

3.3 Arc Length

Theorem 3.7 (Arc Length). *The arc length of the conical helix from $\theta = 0$ to $\theta = T$ is:*

$$L(T) = \frac{a}{2} \left[T\sqrt{T^2 + c^2} + c^2 \operatorname{arcsinh}\left(\frac{T}{c}\right) \right], \quad (13)$$

where

$$c^2 := \frac{a^2 + b^2}{a^2} = 1 + \frac{\pi^2}{4} \approx 3.4674, \quad c \approx 1.8621. \quad (14)$$

Proof. From Theorem 3.2:

$$L(T) = \int_0^T \sqrt{a^2(1 + t^2) + b^2} dt = a \int_0^T \sqrt{t^2 + \frac{a^2 + b^2}{a^2}} dt = a \int_0^T \sqrt{t^2 + c^2} dt.$$

Das Integral $\int \sqrt{t^2 + c^2} dt = \frac{1}{2} [t\sqrt{t^2 + c^2} + c^2 \operatorname{arcsinh}(t/c)]$ is a standard integral [12, 13]. □

Remark 3.1 (The Constant c). The constant $c = \sqrt{1 + \pi^2/4}$ follows directly from the ratio $b/a = \pi/2$ (cf. Remark 1.1). It governs the long-run growth rate of the arc length.

Proposition 3.8 (Asymptotic Arc Length). For $T \rightarrow \infty$:

$$L(T) \sim \frac{a}{2}T^2 = \frac{3}{\pi^2}T^2. \quad (15)$$

Proof. For $T \gg c$: $\sqrt{T^2 + c^2} \approx T$ and $\operatorname{arcsinh}(T/c) \approx \ln(2T/c) = o(T^2)$, so the dominant term is $\frac{a}{2}T^2$. \square

Example 3.1 (Arc Length per Revolution). Arc length of the first five revolutions:

Table 1: Arc length of the conical helix per revolution

Revolution n	θ : from	θ : to	Arc length L
1	0	2π	14.5507
2	2π	4π	36.7221
3	4π	6π	60.4258
4	6π	8π	84.3867
5	8π	10π	108.3747

Cumulative arc length after n full revolutions:

Table 2: Cumulative arc length after n revolutions

Revolutions n	θ_{\max}	$r(\theta_{\max})$	Arc length L
1	2π	3.820	14.5507
2	4π	7.639	51.2728
3	6π	11.459	111.6985
5	10π	19.099	304.2361
10	20π	38.197	1204.9663

4 The Frenet–Serret Frame

4.1 Overview

The *Frenet–Serret frame* (also called the moving trihedron, cf. [4, 8, 5]) is an orthonormal coordinate system that moves along the curve and completely describes its local geometry. Er besteht aus drei Vektoren:

- $\mathbf{T}(\theta)$ – unit tangent vector (direction of motion),

- $\mathbf{N}(\theta)$ – principal normal unit vector (direction of curvature),
- $\mathbf{B}(\theta)$ – binormal unit vector ($\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{T} \times \mathbf{N}$).

4.2 Unit Tangent Vector

Definition 4.1 (Unit Tangent Vector).

$$\mathbf{T}(\theta) = \frac{\dot{\gamma}(\theta)}{|\dot{\gamma}(\theta)|} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^2(1+\theta^2)+b^2}} \begin{pmatrix} a(\cos\theta - \theta \sin\theta) \\ a(\sin\theta + \theta \cos\theta) \\ b \end{pmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

Proposition 4.2 (Pitch Angle). *The angle $\psi(\theta)$ between \mathbf{T} and the xy -plane (pitch angle) is:*

$$\psi(\theta) = \arctan\left(\frac{b}{a\sqrt{1+\theta^2}}\right) = \arctan\left(\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{1+\theta^2}}\right). \quad (17)$$

Remark 4.1. At $\theta \rightarrow 0$: $\psi(0) = \arctan(\pi/2) \approx 57.52^\circ$, exactly the cone angle from Section 2. As $\theta \rightarrow \infty$, $\psi \rightarrow 0^\circ$: the curve becomes increasingly flat.

Table 3: Pitch angle $\psi(\theta)$ of the conical helix

θ	$\psi(\theta)$ (rad)	$\psi(\theta)$ (degrees)
$\theta \rightarrow 0$	1.0039	57.517°
$\pi/2$	0.7007	40.150°
π	0.4446	25.475°
2π	0.2421	13.869°
4π	0.1240	7.103°
10π	0.0499	2.861°

4.3 The Cross Product $\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}$

Lemma 4.3 (Cross Product). *The cross product $\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}$ has components:*

$$(\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma})_x = -ab(2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta), \quad (18)$$

$$(\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma})_y = -ab(2 \sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta), \quad (19)$$

$$(\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma})_z = a^2(2 + \theta^2). \quad (20)$$

Proof. Using $\dot{\gamma}$ from Eq. (9) and $\ddot{\gamma}$ from Eq. (11):

$$\begin{aligned} (\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma})_z &= \dot{x}\ddot{y} - \dot{y}\ddot{x} \\ &= a(\cos\theta - \theta \sin\theta) \cdot a(2 \cos\theta - \theta \sin\theta) \\ &\quad - a(\sin\theta + \theta \cos\theta) \cdot a(-2 \sin\theta - \theta \cos\theta) \\ &= a^2[\cos^2\theta(2 - \theta^2) + \sin^2\theta(2 - \theta^2) + 2\theta^2] \\ &= a^2(2 - \theta^2 + 2\theta^2) = a^2(2 + \theta^2). \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Proposition 4.4 (Norm of the Cross Product).

$$|\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}|^2 = a^2 b^2 (4 + \theta^2) + a^4 (2 + \theta^2)^2. \quad (21)$$

Proof. Inserting Eqs. (18) to (20):

$$\begin{aligned} |\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}|^2 &= a^2 b^2 (2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta)^2 + a^2 b^2 (2 \sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta)^2 + a^4 (2 + \theta^2)^2 \\ &= a^2 b^2 [(2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta)^2 + (2 \sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta)^2] + a^4 (2 + \theta^2)^2 \\ &= a^2 b^2 (4 + \theta^2) + a^4 (2 + \theta^2)^2. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

5 Curvature

Theorem 5.1 (Curvature of the Conical Helix). *The curvature $\kappa(\theta)$ of the conical helix is:*

$$\kappa(\theta) = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 b^2 (4 + \theta^2) + a^4 (2 + \theta^2)^2}}{[a^2 (1 + \theta^2) + b^2]^{3/2}}. \quad (22)$$

Using $b = \frac{\pi}{2}a$, this simplifies to:

$$\kappa(\theta) = \frac{a \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2}{4} (4 + \theta^2) + (2 + \theta^2)^2}}{[a^2 (1 + \theta^2 + \frac{\pi^2}{4})]^{3/2}}. \quad (23)$$

Proof. Follows from the Frenet formula $\kappa = |\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}| / |\dot{\gamma}|^3$ together with Theorems 3.2 and 4.4. \square

Proposition 5.2 (Initial Curvature). *Bei $\theta = 0$ gilt:*

$$\kappa(0) = \frac{2a\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}{(a^2 + b^2)^{3/2}} = \frac{2a}{a^2 + b^2} = \frac{4\pi^2}{3(\pi^2 + 4)} \approx 0.948799. \quad (24)$$

Proof. Setting $\theta = 0$ in Eq. (22), the numerator becomes:

$$\sqrt{a^2 b^2 (4 + 0) + a^4 (2 + 0)^2} = \sqrt{4a^2 b^2 + 4a^4} = 2a\sqrt{b^2 + a^2}.$$

The denominator is $(a^2 \cdot 1 + b^2)^{3/2} = (a^2 + b^2)^{3/2}$. Hence:

$$\kappa(0) = \frac{2a\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}{(a^2 + b^2)^{3/2}} = \frac{2a}{a^2 + b^2}. \quad \square$$

Proposition 5.3 (Asymptotic Curvature). *For $\theta \rightarrow \infty$:*

$$\kappa(\theta) \sim \frac{a}{\theta} = \frac{6}{\pi^2 \theta}. \quad (25)$$

Proof. For large θ : numerator $\sim a^2 \theta^2$, denominator $\sim a^3 \theta^3$, so $\kappa \sim 1/(a\theta)$. \square

Table 4: Curvature and radius of curvature of the conical helix

θ	$\kappa(\theta)$	$\varrho = 1/\kappa$	$ \dot{\gamma}(\theta) $
0	0.948799	1.054	1.1320
$\pi/2$	0.681835	1.467	1.4810
π	0.446906	2.238	2.2201
2π	0.249876	4.002	3.9839
4π	0.129307	7.734	7.7229
10π	0.052256	19.137	19.132

Remark 5.1 (Comparison with the Cylindrical Helix). For a *cylindrical helix* with radius R and pitch h , both curvature $\kappa = R/(R^2 + h^2)$ and torsion $\tau = h/(R^2 + h^2)$ are *constant* [4, 5]. For the conical helix both decrease monotonically ($\kappa \sim 1/\theta$, $\tau \sim 1/\theta^2$) – a fundamental geometric generalisation [7, 6, 18].

6 Torsion

Theorem 6.1 (Torsion of the Conical Helix). *The torsion $\tau(\theta)$ of the conical helix is:*

$$\tau(\theta) = \frac{a^2 b(6 + \theta^2)}{a^2 b^2(4 + \theta^2) + a^4(2 + \theta^2)^2} = \frac{b(6 + \theta^2)}{b^2(4 + \theta^2) + a^2(2 + \theta^2)^2}. \quad (26)$$

Proof. Using the formula $\tau = (\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}) \cdot \ddot{\gamma} / |\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}|^2$.

Numerator. Using $\ddot{\gamma}$ from Eq. (12) and the cross product from Theorem 4.3:

$$\begin{aligned} (\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}) \cdot \ddot{\gamma} &= -ab(2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta) \cdot a(-3 \cos \theta + \theta \sin \theta) \\ &\quad + (-ab)(2 \sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta) \cdot a(-3 \sin \theta - \theta \cos \theta) + 0 \\ &= a^2 b [(2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta)(3 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta) \\ &\quad + (2 \sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta)(3 \sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta)] \\ &= a^2 b [6 \cos^2 \theta + 6 \sin^2 \theta + \theta^2 \cos^2 \theta + \theta^2 \sin^2 \theta] \\ &= a^2 b(6 + \theta^2). \end{aligned}$$

The denominator is $|\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}|^2$ from Theorem 4.4. □

Proposition 6.2 (Asymptotic Torsion). *For $\theta \rightarrow \infty$:*

$$\tau(\theta) \sim \frac{b}{a^2 \theta^2} = \frac{3/\pi}{(6/\pi^2)^2 \theta^2} = \frac{\pi^3}{12 \theta^2}. \quad (27)$$

Table 5: Torsion of the conical helix

θ	$\tau(\theta)$
$\theta \rightarrow 0$	1.11774
$\pi/2$	0.60917
π	0.23417
2π	0.06429
4π	0.01631
10π	0.00262

Proposition 6.3 (Ratio κ/τ). *The ratio of curvature and torsion satisfies:*

$$\frac{\kappa(\theta)}{\tau(\theta)} = \frac{\sqrt{a^2b^2(4 + \theta^2) + a^4(2 + \theta^2)^2}}{a^2b(6 + \theta^2)/(a^2b^2(4 + \theta^2) + a^4(2 + \theta^2)^2)^{1/2}} \cdot \frac{1}{a^2b^2(4 + \theta^2) + a^4(2 + \theta^2)^2}. \quad (28)$$

For $\theta \rightarrow \infty$:

$$\frac{\kappa(\theta)}{\tau(\theta)} \sim \frac{a\theta}{b} = \frac{2\theta}{\pi}. \quad (29)$$

7 Principal Normal and Binormal Vectors

7.1 Principal Normal Vector

Definition 7.1 (Principal Normal Vector). The principal unit normal vector is:

$$\mathbf{N}(\theta) = \frac{1}{\kappa(\theta) |\dot{\gamma}(\theta)|^2} \left(\ddot{\gamma}(\theta) - \frac{\dot{\gamma}(\theta) \cdot \ddot{\gamma}(\theta)}{|\dot{\gamma}(\theta)|^2} \dot{\gamma}(\theta) \right). \quad (30)$$

Lemma 7.2 (Inner Product $\dot{\gamma} \cdot \ddot{\gamma}$).

$$\dot{\gamma} \cdot \ddot{\gamma} = a^2\theta. \quad (31)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\gamma} \cdot \ddot{\gamma} &= a(\cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta) \cdot a(-2 \sin \theta - \theta \cos \theta) \\ &\quad + a(\sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta) \cdot a(2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta) + b \cdot 0. \end{aligned}$$

Expanding the two products individually:

$$\begin{aligned} &a^2(\cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta)(-2 \sin \theta - \theta \cos \theta) \\ &= a^2[-2 \sin \theta \cos \theta - \theta \cos^2 \theta + 2\theta \sin^2 \theta + \theta^2 \sin \theta \cos \theta], \\ &a^2(\sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta)(2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta) \\ &= a^2[2 \sin \theta \cos \theta - \theta \sin^2 \theta + 2\theta \cos^2 \theta - \theta^2 \sin \theta \cos \theta]. \end{aligned}$$

On addition the mixed terms $\pm 2 \sin \theta \cos \theta$ and $\pm \theta^2 \sin \theta \cos \theta$ cancel:

$$\dot{\gamma} \cdot \ddot{\gamma} = a^2[\theta(\cos^2 \theta + \sin^2 \theta)] = a^2\theta. \quad \square$$

7.2 Binormal Vector

Definition 7.3 (Binormal Vector). The unit binormal vector is:

$$\mathbf{B}(\theta) = \mathbf{T}(\theta) \times \mathbf{N}(\theta) = \frac{\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}}{|\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}|}. \quad (32)$$

Example 7.1 (Frenet Frame at $\theta = 2\pi$). At $\theta = 2\pi$, numerically:

$$\mathbf{T}(2\pi) = \begin{pmatrix} 0,15259 \\ 0,95878 \\ 0,23970 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{N}(2\pi) = \begin{pmatrix} -0,98555 \\ 0,16566 \\ -0,03523 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}(2\pi) = \begin{pmatrix} -0,07348 \\ -0,23086 \\ 0,97021 \end{pmatrix}.$$

One verifies: $|\mathbf{T}| = |\mathbf{N}| = |\mathbf{B}| = 1$ and $\mathbf{T} \perp \mathbf{N}$, $\mathbf{T} \perp \mathbf{B}$, $\mathbf{N} \perp \mathbf{B}$.

8 The Frenet–Serret Equations

Theorem 8.1 (Frenet–Serret Equations [9, 10]). *With respect to the natural parametrization (arc length s):*

$$\frac{d\mathbf{T}}{ds} = \kappa \mathbf{N}, \quad \frac{d\mathbf{N}}{ds} = -\kappa \mathbf{T} + \tau \mathbf{B}, \quad \frac{d\mathbf{B}}{ds} = -\tau \mathbf{N}. \quad (33)$$

Remark 8.1. The Frenet–Serret equations describe how the trihedron $(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{B})$ rotates along the curve. Curvature κ governs rotation in the osculating plane; torsion τ governs the twisting about the tangent axis. By Lancret’s theorem [11, 6], a space curve is a (generalised) helix if and only if $\kappa/\tau = \text{const}$. Since for the conical helix $\kappa/\tau \sim 2\theta/\pi \rightarrow \infty$, it is not a helix in this classical sense, but a geometrically richer generalisation.

9 Osculating, Normal, and Rectifying Planes

Definition 9.1 (Planes of the Frenet Frame). At every regular point $\gamma(\theta)$, the Frenet frame defines three distinguished planes:

- **Osculating plane:** spanned by \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{N} ; contains the tangent and the principal normal.
- **Normal plane:** spanned by \mathbf{N} and \mathbf{B} ; perpendicular to the tangent.
- **Rectifying plane:** spanned by \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{B} ; contains the tangent and the binormal.

Proposition 9.2 (Normal Plane Equation). *The normal plane at the point $\gamma(\theta_0)$ has the equation:*

$$\mathbf{T}(\theta_0) \cdot ((x, y, z) - \gamma(\theta_0)) = 0. \quad (34)$$

10 Asymptotic Behaviour

Theorem 10.1 (Asymptotic Behaviour). *As $\theta \rightarrow \infty$, the following asymptotic approximations hold:*

$$|\dot{\gamma}(\theta)| \sim a\theta, \quad (35)$$

$$L(\theta) \sim \frac{a}{2}\theta^2, \quad (36)$$

$$\kappa(\theta) \sim \frac{1}{a\theta} = \frac{\pi^2}{6\theta}, \quad (37)$$

$$\tau(\theta) \sim \frac{b}{a^2\theta^2} = \frac{\pi^3}{12\theta^2}, \quad (38)$$

$$\psi(\theta) \sim \frac{b}{a\theta} = \frac{\pi}{2\theta}. \quad (39)$$

Corollary 10.2 (Asymptotic Ratios). *For $\theta \rightarrow \infty$:*

$$\frac{\kappa(\theta)}{\tau(\theta)} \sim \frac{2\theta}{\pi}, \quad \frac{\kappa(\theta)}{\psi(\theta)} \sim \frac{2}{\pi^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\theta}. \quad (40)$$

Remark 10.1 (Geometric Interpretation). Asymptotically the curve approaches a flat spiral in the xy -plane since $\psi(\theta) \rightarrow 0$ and $\kappa(\theta) \rightarrow 0$. At the same time, the radius $r = a\theta \rightarrow \infty$: the curve moves unboundedly away from the origin.

11 Numerical Curve Points

Table 6: Selected points on the conical helix

θ	$x(\theta)$	$y(\theta)$	$z(\theta)$	$r(\theta)$	$\kappa(\theta)$	$\tau(\theta)$
0	0	0	-0.750	0	0.9488	1.1177
π	-1,905	0	2.250	1.905	0.4469	0.2342
2π	3.810	0	5.250	3.810	0,2499	0.0643
3π	-5,715	0	8.250	5.715	0.1680	0.0286
4π	7.620	0	11.250	7.620	0.1293	0.0163
5π	-9,524	0	14.250	9.524	0.1037	0.0104

12 Summary of Formulae

Table 7: Formula Summary Part 1: Parametrization, Derivatives, and Arc Length

Quantity	Formula
<i>Parametrization</i>	
Constants	$a = \frac{6}{\pi^2} = \frac{1}{\zeta(2)}, \quad b = \frac{3}{\pi}, \quad \frac{b}{a} = \frac{\pi}{2}$
Curve $\gamma(\theta)$	$(a\theta \cos \theta, a\theta \sin \theta, -\frac{3}{4} + b\theta)$
Cone equation	$z = -\frac{3}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2}r$
<i>Derivatives</i>	
$\dot{\gamma}(\theta)$	$(a(\cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta), a(\sin \theta + \theta \cos \theta), b)$
$\ddot{\gamma}(\theta)$	$(a(-2 \sin \theta - \theta \cos \theta), a(2 \cos \theta - \theta \sin \theta), 0)$
$ \dot{\gamma}(\theta) $	$\sqrt{a^2(1 + \theta^2) + b^2}$
<i>Arc Length</i>	
$L(T)$	$\frac{a}{2} \left[T\sqrt{T^2 + c^2} + c^2 \operatorname{arcsinh} \left(\frac{T}{c} \right) \right]$
c^2	$1 + \frac{\pi^2}{4} \approx 3,467$
Asymptotic	$L(T) \sim \frac{a}{2}T^2$

Table 8: Formula Summary Part 2: Frenet Quantities and Identities

Quantity	Formula
<i>Frenet Quantities</i>	
Curvature $\kappa(\theta)$	$\frac{\sqrt{a^2b^2(4 + \theta^2) + a^4(2 + \theta^2)^2}}{[a^2(1 + \theta^2) + b^2]^{3/2}}$
Asymptotic curvature	$\kappa \sim \frac{\pi^2}{6\theta}$
Torsion $\tau(\theta)$	$\frac{b(6 + \theta^2)}{b^2(4 + \theta^2) + a^2(2 + \theta^2)^2}$
Asymptotic torsion	$\tau \sim \frac{\pi^3}{12\theta^2}$
Pitch angle	$\psi = \arctan\left(\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{1 + \theta^2}}\right)$
<i>Identities</i>	
	$\dot{\gamma} \cdot \ddot{\gamma} = a^2\theta$
	$(\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}) \cdot \ddot{\gamma} = a^2b(6 + \theta^2)$
	$\kappa/\tau \sim 2\theta/\pi$

13 Conclusion

This paper has presented a complete differential-geometric analysis of the conical helix $\gamma(\theta) = (a\theta \cos \theta, a\theta \sin \theta, -\frac{3}{4} + b\theta)^T$ präsentiert. The main results are:

1. The curve lies on the cone $z = -\frac{3}{4} + \frac{\pi}{2}r$ (cf. Theorem 2.1), because $b/a = \pi/2$ provides exactly the cone slope.
2. The tangent vector and arc length are given in closed form; the arc length grows asymptotically as θ^2 (cf. Theorems 3.7 and 3.8).
3. Curvature $\kappa \sim 1/\theta$ and torsion $\tau \sim 1/\theta^2$ both decrease monotonically, in contrast to the cylindrical helix with constant values (cf. Theorems 5.1 and 6.1). The non-constant ratio $\kappa/\tau \sim 2\theta/\pi$ confirms by Lancret's theorem that the conical helix is not a classical helix.
4. The triple product $(\dot{\gamma} \times \ddot{\gamma}) \cdot \ddot{\gamma} = a^2b(6 + \theta^2)$ yields an elegant closed form for the torsion (cf. Theorem 6.1).

5. The Frenet frame is completely determined; the Frenet–Serret equations (Theorem 8.1) describe its evolution along the curve.
6. The spiral constant $a = 6/\pi^2 = 1/\zeta(2)$, the reciprocal of the Euler sum, gives the curve a deep number-theoretic connection (cf. Remark 1.1).

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